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AUTOMATIC ATTENDANCE MAINTENANCE SYSTEM BY USING CAMERA AND BIOMETRIC DEVICE

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Abstract

Keeping student attendance record manually has become a tedious task. The attendance record is used while filling up the examination form. Now a day's most of the universities and institutes are allowing candidates to appear for the exam if and only if the attendance of a student is greater than 75% or above. Calculation of this attendance is a tedious task and at the same time innovative devices like biometric and camera can be used to mark the attendance of a student on day-to-day basis. Not only that this attendance can be communicated to the student but also to the parents and others on time to time basis by using mobile phones. Only bio metric attendance is not enough because student may leave the class room by marking the biometric attendance, therefore this attendance is to be checked or verified periodically and finally attendance for the particular student should be kept automatically.

The main aim of this paper is to develop an accurate, fast and very efficient automatic attendance system using biometric fingerprint and periodic checking/verification technique by using camera. This paper tried to put the steps required to mark the attendance sheet by making use of these regular devices in a different way.

Key words: *biometric, fingerprint, camera, verification, attendance*

Introduction:

Keeping the attendance record of a student is very important in all the universities or institutes for checking the performance of student (1). Every institute has its own method in this regard. Most of the institutes till today are taking attendance manually using the attendance book or daily attendance sheet and very few have adopted methods of automatic attendance using some biometric techniques. Some of the institutions have adopted camera based recognition method. But Only Biometric based attendance is not a correct method and use of camera for marking attendance will take a long time for identification and recognition of a student. Many biometric systems are available but the key authentications are same in all the techniques. Every biometric system consists of enrolment process in which unique features of a person is stored in the database and then there are processes of identification and verification.

But only biometric method of recording attendance is not enough because there is a chance that after marking attendance, a student may leave the class, and therefore, a periodic checking of presence of a student in a class is essential to confirm the attendance. Biometric and camera based face recognition verification for those who have marked their biometric attendance will be the best solution for the automatic attendance system. This proposed system takes first biometric attendance and camera based periodic verification will be done for those who have marked their biometric attendance. This process will save the searching time required by the camera for recognition.

Biometric templates can be of many types like Fingerprints, Eye Iris, Face, Hand Geometry, Signature, Gait and voice. Our proposed system uses the biometric device and face recognition approach for the automatic attendance of a student in the class room environment without employees' intervention (2).

Proposed System

This paper focus on the use of combination of two devices. Firstly, biometric device will be used for recognition of a student and camera will be used for verification and checking of presence of a marked student from database for a particular period in the class room.

Biometric Recognition Systems are widely used for unique recognition or identification of human beings mainly for verification and identification. Biometrics is used as a form of identity access management and access control. So use of biometrics in student attendance management system is a secure approach. There are many types of biometric systems like fingerprint recognition, face recognition, voice recognition, iris recognition, palm recognition etc. In this paper, fingerprint recognition system approach is considered.

Fingerprints are considered to be the best and fastest method for biometric identification. They are secure to use, unique for every person and does not change in one's lifetime. Besides these, implementation of fingerprint recognition system is cheap, easy and accurate up to satisfy ability. Fingerprint recognition has been widely used in both forensic and civilian applications. Compared with other biometrics features, fingerprint-based biometrics is the most proven technique and has the largest market shares. Not only it is faster than other techniques but also the energy consumption by such systems is too less.

Managing attendance records of students of an institute is a tedious task. It consumes time and paper both. To make all the attendance related work automatic and on-line, this paper focus on design an attendance management system which could be implemented in any institute. This fingerprint identification system uses existing techniques in fingerprint recognition and matching along with camera verification of only those students who have marked their attendance by using fingerprint is done.

The proposed system consists of a camera that captures the images of the student and sends it to the image enhancement module. After enhancement the image comes in the face detection and recognition modules and then the attendance is marked on the database server. Here it will check the face of a student who has given his fingerprint. This is shown in the experimental setup in Figure (1.0). At the time of enrolment, templates of face images of individual students are stored in the Face database. Here all the faces are detected from the input image and the algorithm compares them one by one with the face database

Figure 1.0 Proposed automatic attendance system

If the face of a student is found and recognized the attendance is marked on the server from where anyone can access and use it for different purposes.

This way a lot of time is saved for searching of face verification for each record and chance of getting successful verification increases and this is highly secure process no one can mark the proxy attendance of other. Attendance is maintained on the server so anyone can access it for purposes like administration, employees themselves (3).

In order to avoid the false detection, the skin classification technique will be used. Using this technique enhances the efficiency and accuracy of the detection process is improved.

Proposed System Algorithm

The algorithm consists of the following steps

1. Biometric Entry at the time of first class begins.
2. Record of present student will be stored on server which will be accessed by camera database further
3. Camera will identify and recognize face of a student
4. Two times randomly camera will confirm the attendance of a student.
5. This attendance is used for the purpose of further report as required.

In the first step biometric presence of a student is marked and this Id is recorded and stored in the server. This record of a student is only referred by camera database for further verification of attendance. Image is captured from the camera. There are illumination effects in the captured image because of different lighting conditions and some noise which is to be removed before going to the next steps (4). Histogram normalization is used for contrast enhancement in the spatial domain. Median filter is used for removal of noise in the image. There are other techniques like FFT and low pass filter for noise removal and smoothing of the images but median filter gives good results.

Attendance Report

This attendance report can be accessed under the report menu, where daily attendance of all students can be generated. The attendance of each student per class per day is stored on the database and can be retrieved. The system was designed to allow the database administrator to view the attendance report of each student as well as a summary report on daily/monthly basis. The report format is shown in Figure 12

Student Id	Name Of The Student	Class	Camera Verification Time 1	Camera Verifi-cation Time 1	Confirm Of Attend.	Date
MCA01	Rohit Choudhari	MCA – I	11.15 am	11.45 am	Yes	12/12/2014
MCA02	Rahul Lele	MCA – I	11.15 am	11.46 am	Yes	12/12/2014

Figure 1.1 Daily Attendance Report of a student

Time table wise attendance of a student can be recorded and a day to day attendance report or monthly attendance report per subject can be measured. Once the record of day to day and subject wise attendance is taken and stored, any type of related reports can be generated which can be reported in printed format of examination form of a student. A sample report is given in figure 1.2

Monthly Report Sample of a Student

Month

Dec

Year

2014

Std Id	Total Attendance for Sub1
MCA01	21/26
MCA02	20/26

Figure 1.2 Monthly Report of a student

Conclusion

In order to reduce the errors and to take the correct attendance, this proposed system envisioned for the purpose of reducing the errors that occur in the traditional (manual) attendance taking system. The aim is to automate and make a system that is useful to any institute. This system can take automatic attendance in efficient and accurately which can replace the old manual method. This proposed method is

secure enough, reliable and will be available for daily use. It can be constructed using a biometric device, camera and computer.

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